

Introducing a New Web Resource for Digital Fieldwork

Qualitative and Multi-Method Research

Fall 2020, Vol. 18, No. 2

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4428970>

Built by researchers for researchers, the Digital Fieldwork website (www.digitalfieldwork.org) (www.digitalfieldwork.org), which will formally launch in mid-February 2021, offers a collaborative forum where scholars with limited ability to conduct traditional fieldwork can help each other to identify and capitalize on data-gathering opportunities, and to explore and address the data-gathering challenges involved in conducting digital fieldwork.

We invite others to join us in this endeavor. Please visit the site and consider contributing material. The site offers three types of content:

- *Resources*: information about events and webinars, organizations and websites, trainings and workshops, as well as collections of digital archival and news media resources related to digital fieldwork.
- *References*: citations for books, articles, and guides on digital fieldwork.
- *Reflections*: original, personal, and experiential thought pieces developed in a variety of media (photo essays, poems, artistic representation, audio, videos, prose, poems, etc.) that discuss how to carry out, manage, or address challenges in conducting digital fieldwork or offer reactions to the experience of doing so.

Traditional field research requires being physically present. Invaluable insights are gained and complex dynamics are understood through the face-to-face interviews, everyday interactions, serendipitous meetings, and discovery of new information sources that fieldwork makes possible.

The COVID-19 pandemic profoundly disrupted how we do fieldwork. Yet it is also the case that fieldwork has been, and will continue to be, out of reach for many scholars around the world for reasons that have little to do with the global health crisis that emerged in 2020. Scholars with limited research budgets often struggle to cover the expenses associated with fieldwork. Additional responsibilities and commitments such as teaching, administrative duties, children, and elder care also restrict scholars' ability to spend time in the field.

In the context of these new and long-standing challenges, technological advances and increased global engagement with technology encourage and facilitate new ways of thinking about and conducting field research. Broadening our conceptualization of fieldwork to include digital techniques can democratize field research, allowing more scholars to imagine conducting fieldwork. Further, accessing digital historical archives, interacting with research interlocutors using digital platforms, and drawing on digital media can catalyze the development of new techniques for data generation and research interaction.

Of course, as we develop new techniques for gathering data, new intellectual, ethical, and practical challenges emerge. How can we protect research subjects and researchers when new tools are used in the contexts and digital spaces in which we work? Whose voices are silenced—and whose are amplified—when fieldwork is conducted digitally? How does conducting human participant research digitally affect the process of gaining approval from Institutional Review Boards (IRBs)? Which technologies are safest? How can our on-the-ground experience with data generation inform our use of digital tools and techniques and help us overcome barriers to employing them? How can researchers determine when it is safe, ethical, and effective to resume on-the-ground fieldwork?

To date, little training has emerged to help scholars wrestle with these questions. We hope this new website will encourage dialogue about the nature of research in a digital age, and about how to accomplish our intellectual goals as ways of thinking about and accessing research sites, participants, and materials evolve.

We invite you to join us. Please visit the website (www.digitalfieldwork.org) – formally launching in mid-February 2021 – and become a contributor. Please also feel free to email Diana Kapiszewski (dk784@georgetown.edu), Lauren MacLean (maclelanl@indiana.edu), or Lahra Smith (Lahra.Smith@georgetown.edu) with comments, queries, or content.